

CINNAMYL ALCOHOL,

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Technical details have been worked out for the preparation of cinnamyl alcohol from cinnamic aldehyde.

Cinnamyl alcohol and its esters are widely used as perfumery components and fixatives. Most important natural source of cinnamyl alcohol is gum styrax in which it occurs in large proportion as cinnamyl cinnamate. Similar esters also occur in Peru and Honduras balsam and in the oil obtained from the bark of *Cinnamomum cassia*, B., which grows to some extent in the West Coast of India. However, major portion of cinnamyl alcohol and its esters used in commerce these days is obtained by synthetic routes. Various methods have been used for this preparation, the basic raw material for which is the easily available cinnamic aldehyde. The latter is commercially obtained by condensation of benzaldehyde with acetaldehyde under specific conditions¹. The method which is almost exclusively used now, is the reduction of cinnamic aldehyde with aluminium alkoxide² of a suitable secondary alcohol in an appropriate solvent. The yield usually is very high and is accompanied by little by-product. The reagent most commonly used is aluminium *iso*-propoxide in *iso*propyl alcohol.

Though the reaction is generally considered to be simple in nature, there are various patents on this preparation so that full technical details about some of the finer points, which are necessary for making a method of practical use, are not available. It is for this reason that this particular preparation has been undertaken in this laboratory, the details of which are incorporated in this paper.

In the preparation of cinnamyl alcohol, *iso*propyl alcohol is usually used as the reaction medium, but a mixture of *iso*propyl alcohol and benzene has been found equally suitable for the reaction. The latter possesses certain advantages which will be mentioned later. Instead of the equipments employed by the earlier workers, a packed column with total condensation partial take off type head was used in the present investigation. This facilitated the continuous removal of acetone by noting the boiling points of the azeotropic mixtures distilling out of the system and made the periodical testing of acetone during the course of the reaction unnecessary. The factor of individual attention was also eliminated. Modifications incorporated in

this paper are likely to introduce considerable economy in the preparation of this compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

Out of the various preliminary experiments the following two methods were found to be most suitable.

Method I.—Cinnamic aldehyde (264 g.), distilled aluminium isopropoxide (68 g.) and isopropyl alcohol (450 c.c.) were taken in a round bottom flask fitted with a column (30") packed with small pieces of glass tubes and fitted with a total condensation partial take off type head and heated on a boiling water-bath. The mixture was allowed to reflux briskly and the mixture of isopropyl alcohol and acetone (formed during the reaction) was slowly tapped out with the help of the distillation head maintaining a high reflux ratio. The distillation temperature initially was 59°-60°/710 mm., which slowly rose with the progress of the reaction. Occasionally isopropyl alcohol was added to compensate the loss during the distillation. The reaction was continued for about 8-10 hours, during which additional isopropyl alcohol (825 c.c.) was added and a mixture of isopropyl alcohol and acetone (900 c.c.) was recovered. The temperature of the distillate at this point was about 80°. The excess of isopropyl alcohol (200 c.c.) from the reaction mixture was then recovered by distillation using an ordinary neck. The product in the flask was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, dried (sodium sulphate), ether removed and the residue distilled under vacuum using a short column when cinnamyl alcohol (200 g.) was obtained, b.p. 100°-102°/1.5 mm. Later on, it was found that pure cinnamyl alcohol could be obtained by direct distillation of the reaction medium without decomposing it with HCl and subsequent extraction with ether. The material crystallised *en masse* into well formed crystals on keeping at room temperature; yield 80%.

Method II.—Cinnamic aldehyde (475 g.), Al isopropoxide (50 g.), isopropyl alcohol (700 c.c.) and benzene (1000 c.c.) were taken in a round bottom flask (5 litre) fitted with the column and the head as described earlier. The mixture was allowed to reflux briskly and the ternary mixture of acetone, benzene and isopropyl alcohol (61.5°) was slowly tapped out. As the reaction proceeded the temperature gradually rose and in about 8 hours reached 69° (the b.p. of the binary mixture of isopropyl alcohol and benzene). The rise of temperature of the distillate to the boiling point of this binary mixture indicates the termination of the reaction.

During the course of the reaction additional quantities of benzene (1000 c.c.) and isopropyl alcohol (300 c.c.) were added to the reaction mixture in arbitrary instalments. The total distillate collected during the entire

course of the reaction was about 500 c.c. The excess of benzene and isopropyl alcohol from the reaction mixture was recovered by distillation (2250 c.c.) and the cinnamyl alcohol collected by direct distillation under vacuum; b.p. 100°-102°/1.5 mm., yield 370 g. (80%). It was free from any traces of aluminium as indicated by quinalizarin test.

Note 1:—The ternary mixture of acetone, isopropyl alcohol and benzene could be used again in subsequent experiments after removing acetone by refluxing over caustic soda, distilling through a column and then treating with lime in the usual way.

Note 2:—The binary mixture of benzene and isopropyl alcohol could be used for the next experiment without any further purification.

Note 3:—Aluminium isopropoxide used in this as well as in Method I, should be the pure distilled product. Attempts to use undistilled* or filtered solutions of aluminium isopropoxide always gave poor yield. Large proportion of a polymeric product was obtained under such conditions. In presence of suspended aluminium powder cinnamyl alcohol was not obtained at all.

Note 4:—In the present investigation 1/10 mol. of the theoretical amount of aluminium isopropoxide gave satisfactory yield. By using a mixture of benzene and isopropyl alcohol, the amount of isopropyl alcohol required was reduced to less than 50% of what had been described in the literature.

Properties of cinnamyl alcohol.—Cinnamyl alcohol, prepared during the present investigation, has the following properties: b.p. 100°-102°/1.5 mm., m.p. 33°; d_4^{20} , 1.0390; n_D^{20} , 1.5770; alcohol content, 99-99.65%, which is within B.P. specification.

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R E F E R E N C E S

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